

INTERFACIAL DECOHESION FAILURE IN A RICE HUSK POWDER EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The increase in consumption of polymer composites has lead researchers towards the potential use of biocomposites for cost reduction. The use of biocomposites, however, can at times reduce the mechanical properties of the composite, which may produce damage and failure under different stresses. Rice husk is one of the most globally available agricultural-waste products. Unlike rice husk ash (RHA), rice husk powder (RHP) is the unmodified form of ground rice husk and requires no burning process for its production. In response to a growing environmental awareness, the use of RHA for composites production is often discouraged. As a result, many researchers have started to explore the potential of RHP as an alternative material to RHA. In order to better understand RHA powder particulate biocomposites for use in non-critical applications, a finite element model was developed to predict the elasto-plastic response as a function of interface strength and to perform damage analysis using ANSYS APDL. This paper deals with 2D analysis of 30 volume percent of rice husk powder in an epoxy resin matrix. The elastic modulus of RHP was 0.77 GPa. The elastic modulus and yield stress of epoxy resin were 2.76 GPa and 42 MPa, respectively. The model was investigated under uniaxial tensile and in-plane shear loadings in order to detect the overall and local damage of the interface between the RHP and the epoxy matrix. It was found that the interfacial failure was related to and led to a sudden slope reduction of the linear hardening region of the stress-strain curve. In addition, it was found that increasing the interfacial strength beyond 40 MPa and 60 MPa for models subjected to uniaxial tensile and shear loadings, respectively, did not affect the slope of the overall stress-strain curve of the biocomposite. Finally, it was found that the interfacial decohesion failure initiates between 1-2% strain.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites have been used in a range of applications for several years [1]. The increase in consumption of polymer composites has lead researchers to the potential use of biocomposites in order to decrease cost [2]. Bio-products of agricultural production such as rice straws and rice husk are on the increase in many developing countries. Most of these bio-products are left at the agricultural site or burned in the fields because it is more difficult and expensive to dispose them [3]. A known caution with using these biocomposites, however is that in some cases, they can reduce the mechanical properties of the composite and produce damage and failure under different stresses [4].

In order to analyze and develop a better understanding of biocomposites, a finite element model was developed to predict elasto-plastic responses and to perform damage analysis using ANSYS APDL. The model consists of 30 volume percent rice husk powder (RHP) in an epoxy resin matrix. The model was loaded under uniaxial tensile and in-plane shear in order to predict the overall and local damage of the interface between the fiber and the matrix. A third element consisting of a cohesive material was used at the interface to simulate decohesion/delamination initiation and propagation of the failure within the epoxy composite.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION

2.1 Element Type

Using ANSYS APDL manual as a reference, the PLANE 183 element was selected. PLANE 183 is a higher order 2-D, 8-noded or 6-noded element with a quadratic displacement behavior and is well suited to modeling irregular meshes. The element has plasticity, hyperelasticity, creep, stress stiffening, large deflection and large strain capabilities (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: PLANE 183 (2-D 8-Noded or 6-Noded Structural Solid)

2.2 Material Properties

The elastic properties of the epoxy matrix and the Rice Husk Powder used in the numerical simulations using ANSYS are given in Table 1 [5].

Parameters		Epoxy Resin	Rice Husk Powder
Young's Modulus (E)	[GPa]	2.76	0.77
Poisson Ratio (ν)	-	0.30	0.39

Table1: Material Properties for Epoxy Resin and Rice Husk Powder

2.3 Nonlinear Model

Bilinear Isotropic Hardening Mises Plasticity was applied to the epoxy resin matrix with the following input parameter as outlined in Table 2. The model was loaded past the yield strength of the epoxy resin matrix, after which plastic deformation was expected to occur.

Parameter		Epoxy Resin
Yield Stress	[MPa]	42.00

Table 2: Bilinear Isotropic Hardening Parameter for Epoxy Resin

2.4 Model and Powder Particle Dimensions

The dimensions of the 2D matrix and powder particle were 0.00012 and 0.00010 m, respectively, which gave it the desired 30 volume percent. These dimensions were used for both tensile and shear loading cases. These values were selected in order to approximate real rice powder dimensions. According to Nielsen et al., the elastic modulus does not depend of the filler fiber size [6]. In addition, it was suggested by Subramanian et al. that the size of the fiber is not considered as important as the volume fraction of reinforcement when calculating the composite's stiffness [7].

2.5 Model Generation

The 2D model was created by using different modeling commands and Boolean operations using ANSYS APDL. First, the RHP particle was created, followed by the matrix.

2.6 Mesh Size and Attribution

A preliminary mesh convergent test was conducted before selecting the right mesh size. The convergence test helped to determine the appropriate number of elements in order to get the most accurate result. The convergent test was performed by first simulating the test with a few elements and then with many elements, allowing a comparison as to which test performed better. After analyzing the model, an average number of 315 elements were used for the simulations. Before the model was ready to be meshed, the material properties for each element were assigned.

2.7 Boundary Conditions

Symmetric boundary conditions were applied on the left and the bottom side of the model subjected to uniaxial tensile loading. In the case of the in-plane shear simulation; symmetry was applied only on the left side. In addition, the left side was constrained in the y-direction.

The use of coupled degrees of freedom was also implemented in the uniaxial tensile simulation model on the nodes on the top side in the y-direction. In addition, the nodes on the right side were coupled in the x-direction (Fig. 2 (a)). In the case of the in-plane shear simulation, the top, right and bottom side nodes were constrained in the x-direction, and the right side nodes were coupled in the y-direction (Fig. 2 (b)).

Figure 2: (a) Tensile couple degrees of freedom, and (b) Shear couple degrees of freedom

2.8 Applied Stress

A uniaxial tensile loading and shear loading of 50 MPa and 30 MPa, respectively, were applied during the simulations. The loads were approximately 1.2 times the initial yield stress for each case of the elasto-plastic epoxy. The load values were determined from the stress vs. strain curve from the simulation assuming a perfect interfacial adhesion between the fiber and matrix materials [5]. The initial shear yield stress was calculated using eqn. 1 and von Mises' criterion.

$$k = \frac{\sigma_y}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (1)$$

k - yield stress of the material in pure shear, σ_y - tensile yield stress

2.9 Load Steps

In order to get the most accurate results for these nonlinear problems, the load was subdivided into a series of load increment steps and substeps. Both maximum and minimum substep numbers were selected for the simulations to assure convergence without errors (Table 3).

Load steps	1000
Maximum substeps	5000
Minimum substeps	1000

Table 3: Load steps and substeps setting

3 MODELING INTERFACIAL DECOHESION WITH INTERFACE ELEMENT

In order for the 2D model to simulate decohesion initiation and propagation failure, the use of a third element (cohesive material) is implemented within the RHP-epoxy composite.

3.1 Cohesive Element Type

Again using ANSYS APDL manual as a reference, the INTER 203 was selected. INTER 203 is a 2-D 6-noded quadratic element used for 2-D structural assembly modeling. This element provides an interfacial surface and can be used to model subsequential delamination process. The separation is represented by an increasing displacement between nodes which are originally coincident. The element has two degrees of freedom at each node, giving the translations needed in the nodal x and y directions.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Stress evolution at micro-scale

Figure 3 (a) shows the contour plot of SY stress under uniaxial tensile loading at the yield point of 42 MPa. As shown in the plot, the maximum stress is located at the bottom next to the interface of the two materials; also shown is that maximum stress region is located within the matrix material as it has the higher Young's modulus. Figure 3 (b) shows the contour plot of SXY stress under in-plane shear loading at the yield point of 25 MPa. In this case, the maximum stress is at the top left of the model, due the same concept explained above.

Figure 3: (a) Contour plot of SY stress under uniaxial tensile loading, and (b) Contour plot of SXY stress under in-plane shear loading

4.2 Effect of the interface strength on the overall stress-strain response

Figures 4 and 5 show the overall stress-strain response of the composite under uniaxial tensile and in-plane shear loadings, respectively. It is found that the interfacial failure is related to and leads to a sudden slope reduction of the linear hardening region of the stress-strain curve. It is also found that increasing the interfacial strength beyond 40 MPa and 60 MPa for the uniaxial tensile (Fig. 4) and in-plane shear (Fig. 5) loadings does not have a significant effect on the overall stress-strain curve.

Figure 4: Overall uniaxial tensile stress-strain response with different bonding strength between the fiber and the matrix

Figure 5: Overall in-plane shear stress-strain response with different bonding strength between the fiber and the matrix

4.3 Debonding initiation and progression between the fiber and the matrix

Figure 6 (a) shows the interfacial separation during uniaxial tensile loading. The initial decohesion and interface separation is seen starting at the top of the interface at about 1% strain (Fig. 4). Figure 6 (b) shows the progression of debonding increases dramatically at the top side of the interface.

Figure 6: (a) Interfacial debonding initiation under uniaxial loading at 42 MPa, and (b) Interfacial debonding propagation under uniaxial loading at 50 MPa

Figure 7 (a) shows the interfacial separation during in-plane shear loading. The initial decohesion interface separation is shown to start at the center of the interface at about 2% strain (Fig. 5). Figure 7 (b) shows how the progression of debonding increases dramatically at the center of the interface, this is due the stress concentration at the center of the model created by the shear load.

Figure 7: (a) Interfacial debonding initiation under in-plane shear loading at 25 MPa, and (b) Interfacial debonding propagation under in-plane shear loading at 30 MPa

5 CONCLUSIONS

A finite element 2D model was developed to predict elasto-plastic responses and to perform damage analysis using ANSYS APDL. The model was investigated under uniaxial tensile and shear loadings. The implementation of a third element, a cohesive material, was critically important for the prediction of the failure at the interface between the matrix and the fiber. Several important conclusions can be drawn from this work:

1. It was found that the interfacial failure was related to and led to a sudden slope reduction of the linear hardening region of the stress-strain curve.
2. Increasing the interfacial strength beyond 40 MPa and 60 MPa for models subject to tensile and shear loadings does not appear to affect the overall stress-strain curve of the biocomposite.
3. The model captured details of interfacial failure, and it was found that the interfacial failure initiated at about 1% strain for uniaxial tensile loading and about 2% strain for in-plane shear loading.

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